

LIFETIME PREDICTION OF SELF-HEALING CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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1 Introduction

SiC/SiC ceramic matrix composites are receiving particular attention in a wide range of specialized aeronautical applications. Herakles (Safran) realized recently a first in the world of civil aviation, by testing an engine equipped with an exhaust cone gas in ceramic matrix composites (CMCs). Able to withstand temperatures ranging from 1000 to 1500°C, CMCs are particularly suitable for mechanical parts that are exposed to high temperatures, for instance, the heat of the engines. Moreover, they should also provide weight savings compared to metal parts. The domain of civil aviation started to be explored in order to mass-produce parts that could equip the next generation of engines. Unlike the military field, where the number of hours flown by an aircraft is limited, civil aircraft engines are highly solicited. In addition to a strong resistance at high temperatures, the parts must have a long lifetime.

To meet the expectations of civil aerospace, silicon carbide fibres are used. However SiC/SiC ceramic composites constituents are intrinsically oxidation-prone. Therefore the most significant problem that SiC/SiC composites present, is the oxidation embrittlement [1]. Typically, the embrittlement occurs once oxygen enters through the matrix cracks and reacts with the fibres and the fibre coatings [2-4]. Composite degradation may be further accelerated by cyclic loading, where the reaction gases are expelled from matrix cracks during unloading and oxidizing atmosphere is drawn into the composite through the matrix cracks during reloading [1]. The issue of improving the oxidation

resistance of the SiC/SiC composites has been addressed through the design of innovative multilayered interphases [5-7] and of self-healing multilayered matrices [5-11]. The multilayered matrices contain phases that facilitate glass formation at high temperatures thus healing the cracks and preventing oxygen from diffusing further into the composite and reaching the oxidation-prone fibres. This property is essential for achieving 100,000 hours of operation required by a civil engine part. As a thorough understanding of fatigue performance of SiC/SiC composites in service environments is critical to design with and predict life for these materials, several recent studies investigated experimentally mechanical behaviour of high performance SiC/SiC composites.

From a modelling point of view, different studies have been lead to describe and to model the oxidation of fibres, matrices and interfaces. Casas [13] proposed to incorporate the effects of the oxidation of constituents into the mechanical response of the material by accounting for the creep-oxidation interactions at high temperature. The model predictions illustrate the effect of oxidation on the creep life of the material and highlight the important role of carbon layer oxidation and matrix oxidation. It also shows that matrix cracking causes a progressive overloading of the fibres. This, combined with the degradation of fibres in time, causes final failure. This model is valid only for high temperatures (1000°C-1100°C) but turbine blades are subjected to a gradient of temperature between 600°C and 1100°C from the bottom to the top and the bottom is the most solicited part of the blade.

An appropriate simulation of the behavior and lifetime of composites with self-healing ceramic matrix requires the coupling of models issued from both mechanics and chemistry. The interphase surrounding the fibres is commonly introduced to deflect matrix cracks in the direction of the fibres [11]. The degradation of this interphase results in the opening of the cracks perpendicular to the fibres. A model of the crack opening, matrix healing and fibre strength degradation mechanisms as functions of oxygen concentration was proposed in [14, 15]. This model does not take into account the coupling of mechanical and physicochemical mechanisms with time. The physicochemical model is applied as post-treatment of the mechanical one. Moreover, instantaneous oxidation of the pyrocarbon interphase is considered in this model instead of a progressive one which implies a modulus reduction, a residual deformation augmentation and a load transfer to intact fibres.

In this work an approach able to predict the lifetime of SiC/SiC woven ceramic matrix composites is proposed where a macroscopic mechanical model and a physicochemical model are coupled with time. The procedure is validated considering SiC/SiC specimens under fatigue loadings and subjected to different kind of environment, i.e. pressure (oxygen and water), temperature. For reasons of confidentiality, no experimental result will be shown. Only trend curves will be presented in this paper.

2 The mechanical model

The nonlinear behavior of CMCs until failure is the result of various degradation mechanisms: initiation of matrix-cracks at macropores, inter-yarn matrix cracking, yarn/matrix interface and yarn/yarn interface debonding, and fibre fracture [16]. The mechanical model used in this work is based on the static damage model developed at ONERA [17]. This macroscopic model is built within the continuum damage mechanics framework and describes the aforementioned degradation mechanisms. It is based on the Helmholtz free energy. This thermodynamic potential is function of the state variables, separated into observable ones (the temperature T and the total strain tensor ε) and internal ones (elastic and plastic strain tensor, damage tensor, etc.). Figure 1 outlines the link

between the loading direction and the scalar damage variables employed in the formulation.

The mechanical damage model describes the physical phenomena experimentally observed in woven CMC materials: (1) the effect of damage on the elastic behavior, (2) the unilateral character of damage (the effect of damage depends on the micro-crack opening), and (3) the residual strain (linked both to damage and manufacture processes). Moreover, the effects of progressive failure is introduced into the model. Figure 2 describes the behavior of CMCs composite.

Some modifications have been made in the model proposed in [17]. The definition of the positive part of the total strain tensor is now based on the determination of an efficient strain for each direction of damage. The thermodynamic forces are then redefined as function of this new formulation based on the positive deformations. Another modification concerns the plane/out-of-plane coupling as shown in Fig. 1. To represent out-of-plane cracks, which means the interface debonding between warp and weft yarns, a plane/out-of-plane coupling has been introduced. Moreover, the thermodynamic forces of the fibres have also been modified to take into account the shear effect on the yarns rupture. To deal with fatigue loadings, the model has been extended to describe their impact on the mechanical properties of the material. The main assumption is that static and fatigue damage mechanisms are the same.

During a creep or fatigue solicitation, the matrix damage variable d_m evolves in function of the number of cycles N , the characteristic parameters of the cycle (maximal stress, the thermodynamic force ratio $R_{y(i)}$) and the damage generated by the previous cycles:

$$\frac{\partial d_m}{\partial N} = \frac{g_y}{\lambda \cdot d_c} \cdot (d_c - d_m)^{(1+\lambda)} \cdot (d_m)^{(1-\lambda)} \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{1}{g_y} \left(\frac{dm}{d_c - dm}\right)^\lambda\right)$$

with

$$g_y = (1 - R_y)^\beta \left(\frac{\langle y_{\max}^{(m)} - y_{\max}^{Fatigue} \rangle_+}{y_c^{Fatigue}} \right)^\delta$$

and

$$R_{y_i} = \frac{y_i^{\max}}{y_i^{\min}} \text{ avec } \begin{cases} y_i^{\max} = \max_{\text{sur le cycle}} (y_i(\varepsilon)) \\ y_i^{\min} = \min_{\text{sur le cycle}} (y_i(\varepsilon)) \end{cases}, i = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$$

where d_c represents the saturation value of damage evaluated experimentally, $y_0^{Fatigue}$ the thermodynamic force threshold in fatigue, y_i the thermodynamic forces of the matrix and α, γ, δ material parameters.

An extensive network of matrix cracks forms during tension-compression cycling. This model is able to provide the crack network indicators and the opening states of the cracks as functions of the loading. The matrix cracks' opening evolves as a function of the loading. To take into account the cycles, the matrix cracks' opening in the mechanical model depends on a progressive deactivation index $\eta_i(\varepsilon)$ defined in such a way that if $\eta_i = 1$, all the cracks in direction i are open and $\eta_i = 0$, they are all closed. This index depends on the damage and allows to take into account the damage influence on the intermediate area between a state where cracks are all open and state where they are all closed.

As described on fig.3, a crack opening h^m is defined as

$$h^m = h_0^m \langle d - d_{\text{threshold}} \rangle_+ \eta \varepsilon$$

with $d_{\text{threshold}}$ a damage threshold. This crack opening enables to determine the pressure of oxygen inside the composite as following:

$$P_{O_2}^{\text{int}} = \frac{h^m}{1 + h^m} P_{O_2}^{\text{ext}} \quad \text{with } P_{O_2}^{\text{ext}} \text{ the external}$$

pressure. Thus, if the crack opening is very important, the oxygen pressure in the material tends to be the external pressure. Otherwise, if the cracks are closed, the oxygen pressure in the composite is zero.

For any complex static or fatigue loading [12], this mechanical macromodelling enables the calculation of the opening indicator value for the cracks perpendicular to the fibre strands. This indicator constitutes the link between the mechanical model and the oxidation model.

3 The physical-chemistry model

The extensive network of matrix cracks which forms during tension–compression cycling exposes the composite to oxidation embrittlement. Then the multilayered self-healing matrix can no longer protect the composite against the environmental ingress. Oxygen goes through the cracks, degrades the fiber–matrix interphase and, at high temperatures (>650°C), forms a glass that fills the cracks and plays the role of a plug which slows the diffusion of oxygen. This oxidizing environment has consequently a strong influence on brittle fracture along the fibres. The failure threshold of the fibres evolves, attributed to subcritical cracking of the fibre.

3.1 Oxidation of the pyrocarbon layer

The pyrocarbon (PyC) layer enables to deviate cracks in a direction parallel to the fibres and delays the fibre oxidation. Under a mechanical solicitation, cracking appears, thus facilitating the ingress of the oxygen present in the macropores or in the external environment (Fig.4). Then the oxygen reaches the pyrocarbon layer before the fibres. Under oxidizing environment at temperatures between 450°C and 650°C, pyrocarbon oxidizes and the thickness of the pyrocarbon e_{PyC}^{vol} vanishes (Fig.5a). The remaining thickness e_{PyC}^{rem} decreases and once there is no more PyC left, the oxygen can reach the fibre (Fig. 5b) and leads to the failure of the composite. Therefore, the oxidation leads to a carbon oxide, then to a carbon dioxide which make the oxygen diffusion towards the pyrocarbon more difficult [18] (Fig. 6a). In the proposed model, the evolution of the PyC thickness with time depends on the oxygen concentration, close to the interphase ($C_{O_2}^{PyC}$) as shown in Fig. 6b. The oxidation of the PyC follows an Arrhenius law as:

$$\frac{\partial e_{PyC}^{vol}}{\partial t} = \alpha_{e_{PyC}} k_0^{PyC} \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{E_a^{PyC}}{RT(t)}\right) \left(C_{O_2}^{PyC}(t)\right)^n$$

where $\alpha_{e_{PyC}}$ is a material constant, k_0^{PyC} is a reaction constant [$m^{3n+1} \cdot \text{mol}^{-n} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$], E_a^{PyC} the activation energy [$\text{J} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$], R is the universal gas constant, T is the temperature [kelvins], $C_{O_2}^{PyC}$ is the molar

concentration in oxygen at the interphase [mol.L⁻¹] and n the reaction order.

The concentration of oxygen at the interphase is given by:

$$C_{O_2}^{PyC}(t) = \frac{C_{O_2}^{int}(t)}{1 + \frac{e_{PyC}^{vol}(t) S_{PyC}}{D S_{Diff}} k_0^{PyC} \exp\left(-\frac{E_a^{PyC}}{RT(t)}\right)}$$

By solving these equations the remaining PyC thickness around the fibre is calculated using the following relation:

$$e_{remained}^{PyC} = e_{PyC}^{init} - \int_0^t de_{PyC}^{vol}$$

By knowing the thickness of pyrocarbon left between the fibre and the crack, the time when the fibres will start to oxidize can be determined. Then the time during where the fiber is protected by pyrocarbon will be shorter as the temperature or the oxygen pressure is high (Fig. 7). Once the thickness of pyrocarbon in front of the crack is completely consumed, the oxygen present in the composite will attack both the strands and the remaining pyrocarbon along the strands (Fig. 8a) and will create a debonding length l^{PyC} as shown schematically in Fig. 7b.

The PyC length l^{PyC} evolves in the same way as the thickness e^{PyC} in function of the environment as following:

$$\frac{\partial l_{PyC}^{vol}}{\partial t} = \alpha_{l_{PyC}} k_0^{PyC} \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{E_a^{PyC}}{RT(t)}\right) \left(C_{O_2}^{l_{PyC}}(t)\right)^n$$

where $\alpha_{l_{PyC}}$ is a material parameter. Then, the concentration of oxygen at the interphase is a function of l^{PyC} :

$$C_{O_2}^{l_{PyC}}(t) = \frac{C_{O_2}^{int}(t)}{1 + \frac{l_{PyC}^{vol}(t) S_{PyC}}{D S_{Diff}} k_0^{PyC} \exp\left(-\frac{E_a^{PyC}}{RT(t)}\right)}$$

Experimental tests have shown that the oxidation of the PyC interphase leads to a reduction of the compliance tensor. For this reason, a fibre/matrix debonding rate β^{decoh} has been added in the evaluation of the matrix compliance tensor and

enables to link the mechanical model with the physicochemical one. This dimensionless function represents the average debonding fibre length \bar{l}^{PyC} in a yarn so that $\beta^{decoh} = f(\bar{l}^{PyC})$. Then, the more important the debonding lengths are i.e. the more important the interphase oxidation is, the more influent the debonding rate will be on the global behaviour of the composite.

The compliance of the material is written:

$$\Delta \underline{S} = f(d_1^m, \chi^{decoh}, \beta^{decoh}, \eta_1^m)$$

when χ^{decoh} a material coefficient that takes into account the effect of the interphase oxidation on the compliance tensor. Moreover, the residual strain will increase according to $\underline{\varepsilon}^r = f(d_1^m, \zeta^{decoh}, \beta^{decoh}, \eta_1^m)$

where ζ^{decoh} is a coefficient to determine. The key assumption in the modelling of the lifetime is that under in-plane loading of the composite the material's lifetime is governed by the ultimate strength of the fibres, and then the lifetime of the composite can be determined once the failure is reached as:

$$\left(1 + \alpha_{Rt} \left(\frac{d_1^m}{d_{c1}^{mf}} + \gamma^{decoh} \beta^{decoh}\right)^{n_{Rt}}\right) y_{1t}^{toron} \geq y_{01t}^{toron}$$

3.2 Yarns oxidation

The lifetime of CMCs depends not only on the temperature but also on the pressure of oxygen which penetrates in the composite. The oxygen pressure is even greater in a damaged composite. Indeed, the increase of damage in the material will result in a more extended cracks network which constitutes a preferred way to transport oxygen to the strands. Thus, the more the material is damaged, the more the fibres will break prematurely. At temperatures below 900°C, Nicalon fibres have fragile elastic behaviour, but in an oxidizing environment at temperatures greater than 450°C and under mechanical loading, their ultimate strength decreases. Then a crack propagation process within the fibre takes place [23]. To account for the fracture of the Nicalon fibres, the failure thresholds of the yarn decrease with the temperature T and the oxygen concentration $C_{O_2}^{int}$ in the material so

that $y_0^{yarn} = f(T, C_{O_2}^{int})$ and the evolution of the threshold is a function of the evolution of the failure stress of the yarn noted as σ_r^{yarn} :

$$\frac{dy_0^{yarn}(t)}{dt} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{2E_{11}^{yarn}}} y_{0_i}^{yarn} \frac{d\sigma_r^{yarn}(t)}{dt}$$

From experimental work [19, 20] it has been shown that the evolution law of the ultimate strength of the yarns has been determined in the composite as following:

$$\frac{d\sigma_r^{yarn}(t)}{dt} = -\frac{1}{n} \frac{1}{B} \frac{d\theta}{dt} (\sigma_r^{yarn}(t))^{n+1}$$

with n and B material coefficients and the parameter θ defined as

$$\theta = \int_0^t C_{O_2}(\tau) \exp\left(-\frac{Ea}{RT(\tau)}\right) d\tau$$

weighted by the temperature and the oxygen concentration. Based on these works, the evolution law of the threshold is defined as

$$\frac{dy_{0_{it}}^{yarn}(t)}{dt} = -\frac{1}{\bar{B}} \cdot C_{O_2}^{int}(t) \exp\left(-\frac{E_a^{Nicalon}}{RT(t)}\right) (y_{0_{it}}^{yarn}(t))^{\frac{n}{2}+1}$$

where $\bar{B} = \frac{nB}{2} (2E_{11}^{yarn})^{-\frac{n}{2}}$, n and $E_a^{Nicalon}$ are coefficients identified on fatigue tests on Nicalon yarns ([20,21]).

According to the relationship of the ideal gas, the molar concentration $C_{O_2}^{int}$ is connected to the oxygen pressure in the heart of the material by the following relation:

$$C_{O_2}^{int}(t) = \frac{P_{O_2}^{int}(t)}{RT(t)}$$

The evolution law of the threshold decreases more rapidly as temperature and oxygen pressure increases, as shown on fig. 9. As mentioned

previously, this damage model is valid only for low and intermediate temperatures ($T < 650^\circ\text{C}$). For higher temperature ($T > 650^\circ\text{C}$), a new phenomenon appears: the self-healing of the cracks which will prevent oxygen from diffusing further into the composite and reaching the oxidation-prone fibres.

3.3 Self-healing

The physical-chemistry model is able to determine the oxygen concentration reaching the fibres due to the opening states of the cracks. This quantity is function of the oxygen pressure but it is limited by the self-healing behaviour of the matrix and the oxidation of the interphase. The self-healing mechanism is modelled by creating an oxide plug in an open crack and simulating the diffusion of oxygen through its evolving geometry. The self-healing process is important at high temperatures ($T > 650^\circ\text{C}$). At intermediate temperatures ($\sim 450^\circ\text{C}$), the self-healing contribution is negligible and the oxidation process has a major impact on the evolution law for fibre strength.

At temperatures ranging between 400°C and 700°C , the main active matrix layer is a boron carbide (B_4C). In the presence of oxygen, the oxidation reaction leads to a boron oxide (B_2O_3). The description of the formation of the plug is associated with the mechanism of oxygen diffusion through the plug. However in a humid atmosphere, this plug volatilizes in the presence of water vapour. In addition, volatilization is also observed for temperatures above 850°C . The volatilization of the oxide due to the temperature in the presence of water may result in a reduction of the volume of the plug (cf. fig. 10). Then, the oxidation rate during healing is described in this study by the sum of different rates:

$$\frac{\partial h_{B_2O_3}}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial h_{B_2O_3}^{created O_2}}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial h_{B_2O_3}^{volIT}}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial h_{B_2O_3}^{volH_2O}}{\partial t}$$

where

i) the oxidation rate of the $B_2O_3(l)$ created by oxygen is defined as following:

$$\frac{\partial h_{B_2O_3}^{created}}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{2h_{B_2O_3}^{created}(t)} k_0^f \exp\left(-\frac{E_a^f}{RT(t)}\right) (P_{O_2}^{ext}(t))^n$$

ii) the rate of B_2O_3 volatilized by water vapor is defined as following:

$$\frac{\partial h_{B_2O_3}^{volH_2O}}{\partial t} = k_0^{volH_2O} \exp\left(-\frac{E_a^{volH_2O}}{RT(t)}\right) (P_{H_2O}(t))^m$$

iii) the rate of B_2O_3 volatilized above $850^\circ C$ is defined as following:

$$\frac{\partial h_{B_2O_3}^{volT}}{\partial t} = h_v (T(t) - T_{volT}^{B_2O_3}) k_0^{volT} \exp\left(-\frac{E_a^{volT}}{RT(t)}\right) \quad \text{with}$$

$$h_v (T(t) - T_{volT}^{B_2O_3}) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } T(t) < T_{volT}^{B_2O_3} \\ 1 & \text{if } T(t) \geq T_{volT}^{B_2O_3} \end{cases}$$

where $T_{volT}^{B_2O_3}$, k_0^f , $k_0^{volH_2O}$, k_0^{volT} , E_a^f , $E_a^{volH_2O}$, E_a^{volT} , n and m are parameters determined in [21,22].

The healed matrix opening h_{ouv} , described in fig.11 is determined as:

$$h^{ouv}(t) = h^m(t) - h_{B_2O_3}(t).$$

The fig.12 presents the influence of the temperature on the lifetime of the composite. It shows that when healing is taken into account, the lifetime increases above $650^\circ C$ as expected.

4 Coupling between the mechanical and the physical-chemistry models

The coupling between the mechanical model and the physical-chemistry model (Fig12) is done as following: the fatigue loading is partitioned in different blocks as function of the number of cycles. The mechanical model determines the damage evolution, i.e. crack density and opening, due to fatigue loading at the end of each block of cycles before moving to the next block. The effects of the oxidation on the mechanical properties is also evaluated at the end of each block using the physical-chemistry model. If the temperature is greater than $450^\circ C$ the self healing process is also taken into account. The oxygen quantity reaching the fibre is then estimated and used to determine the lifetime of the structure. This process is repeated at the end of each block of cycles during the fatigue loading. The process is illustrated on Fig. 13.

5 Conclusions

A mechanical/physicochemical model has been proposed to predict the lifetime of CMC composites with self-healing matrix. It was shown that it is important to take into account the coupling of

mechanical and physicochemical mechanisms into a single tool to predict the behaviour of these materials in a structure subjected to complex thermomechanical solicitations in an oxidizing environment. This model describes all the major trends of the different observed phenomena. The accuracy of the proposed procedure needs to be validated by taking into account experimental data obtained at different ranges of temperature.

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Fig. 1. Scalar damage variables used in the model.

Fig. 2. Stress-strain curve for describing the behavior of CMCs composite.

Fig. 3. Inter-yarn matrix crack in a longitudinal yarn in a cell of length L.

Fig. 4. Oxygen arriving to the fibre (SHM : self healing matrix)

a. Volatilization of the pyrocarbon layer.

b. Oxygen reaching the fibre

Fig. 5. Different steps of the volatilization of the pyrocarbon layer.

Fig. 7. Influence of the temperature under 20kPa of O_2 and influence of the oxygen pressure at 450°C.

Fig. 6. Formation of CO_2 during the oxidation of the PyC layer.

Fig. 8. Oxidation of the interphase: step 1 (left) and step 2 (right)

Fig. 9. Influence of the temperature for an oxygen pressure of 20kPa and influence of the oxygen pressure at 600°C on the failure threshold of the yarns

Fig. 10. Self-healing mechanism during the crack opening.

Fig. 11. Determination of the opening h_{ow} during the formation of the plug

Fig. 12. Influence of the self-healing on the lifetime ($R = 0$, $f=20\text{Hz}$, $P_{O_2} = 2\text{kPa}$, $P_{H_2O} = 0 \text{ Pa}$)

Fig. 13. Coupling between the mechanical and the physical-chemistry models.

Fig. 14. Flow chart of the proposed model including both the mechanical and physicochemical contribution.